

HEAT OF WETTING OF ANIMAL CHARCOAL BY DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

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The relationship between the heat of wetting of animal charcoal by different solvents and the adsorption of aromatic acids and hydrocarbons have been discussed. It has been found that the adsorption of naphthalene and acenaphthene decreases as the heat of wetting decreases, but on the other hand, in the case of acids, reverse relation is true which is probably due to the presence of the polar group in the acids.

Pouillet (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1822, 20, 141) noted a rise in temperature when a fine powder was brought in contact with a liquid having apparently no solvent or chemical action on the powder. The heat evolved, when one gram of powder is immersed in a liquid, is called the heat of wetting or the heat of immersion of the powder.

When charcoal is dropped into a liquid, the liquid penetrates the charcoal with the result that the solid-gas interface disappears and a new liquid-solid interface appears in place of the former. If the charcoal possesses initially a surface tension γ_{so} and the specific area, α , and after immersion the interfacial tension becomes γ_{sl} and the surface area α' , then according to Williams (*Proc. Roy. Soc. Edin.*, 1917, 18, 38, 23) the heat of immersion of one gram of charcoal will be

$$-H = \alpha \left(\gamma_{so} - T \frac{d\gamma_{so}}{dT} \right) - \alpha' \left(\gamma_{sl} - T \frac{d\gamma_{sl}}{dT} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

With a solid adsorbent like charcoal, where swelling is of a small order of magnitude, the surface is not appreciably altered by the wetting process and the equation becomes after taking $\alpha = \alpha'$,

$$-H = \alpha (\gamma_{so} - \gamma_{sl}) - \alpha T \left(\frac{d\gamma_{so}}{dT} - \frac{d\gamma_{sl}}{dT} \right) \quad \dots (2)$$

On neglecting the variation of surface tension,

$$-H = \alpha (\gamma_{so} - \gamma_{sl}) = \alpha A_{(s-l)} \quad \dots (3)$$

where $A_{(s-l)}$ is the adhesion tension of liquid A against the solid charcoal and is equal to $(\gamma_{so} - \gamma_{sl})$ by definition. From the above equation it is clear that on wetting an amount of heat is set free which is equivalent to the decrease in surface tension.

Gibbs adsorption equation also gives a relation between the adsorption and the decrease in surface tension, and so here appears a kind of resemblance between adsorption and the heat of wetting. The present work was undertaken with a view to ascertaining whether or not it was possible to account for the heat of wetting of animal charcoal on the basis of adsorption from solutions.

During the process of adsorption, adsorbent added is not free from air, and therefore work on wetting has been done with the adsorbent exposed to air. Evidently the surface is covered in such cases with an adsorbed film of air or of some of its constituents. The effect of such an adsorbed film is to retard the wetting process and also to

introduce energy changes accompanying its displacement (Razouk, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1941, 45, 180). Therefore, values thus determined will not be very correct, but a comparative idea can be formed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Purification of Chemicals.—All the wetting liquids were of the best quality. They were purified and dried according to standard methods. Animal charcoal used was chemically pure and was free from phosphate and chloride. It was sieved through 3600/sq. cm. mesh. It was used after drying at 110°.

Apparatus.—The apparatus is similar in type to that of Patric and Grim (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 2144). The calorimeter was a Dewar flask stoppered with a well fitted cork through which passed two thermometers (one of the Beckmann type and the other, an ordinary graduated up to 50°C), the heater, stirrer and stoppered tube open at both ends containing animal charcoal. The heater consisted of a manganin coil of resistance nearly four ohms, wound around the closed end of a glass tube and soldered to thick copper leads. The resistance was accurately determined at the end of each experiment by meter bridge.

The calorimeter was fitted up and then put in a thermostat, the temperature of which was kept constant. When equilibrium conditions were established, the stopper at the lower end of the tube containing charcoal was opened by pushing from above. The rise in temperature was observed and corrected for the loss of radiation and conduction. At the end of each experiment the heat capacity of the system was determined by measuring the temperature rise due to the passage of known electric current through the heating coil for a definite period of time. The current was measured by depositing silver in series with the experiment. The coulometer solution was as suggested by Wartenberg and Schutzka, (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1930, 36, 254).

Results obtained are given in Table I along with the values of the substances adsorbed at 0.2M concentration in millimoles/litre. Values of heat of wetting are the mean of

TABLE I

Solvent.	Heat of wetting (cal/g.).	Adsorption in millimoles/litre at 0.2M concentration				
		Benzoic acid.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.	Phthalic acid. (0.2N).	Naphthalene.	Acenaphthene.
MeOH	33.82	31.2	39.4	37.9	45.6	61.6
EtOH	32.97	31.0	46.4	34.5*	41.7	58.4
<i>n</i> -PrOH	31.46	30.8	53.5	64.9	31.1	42.5
<i>n</i> -BuOH	30.59	30.7	58.3	66.8	28.2	39.7
Acetone	30.02	28.2*	34.7*	46.5*	27.6	38.9
Acetic acid	25.48	28.9*	—	—	28.2	37.1
Benzene	17.44	43.5	—	—	15.5	27.6
Toluene	17.14	40.2	—	—	12.10	25.9
Chlorobenzene	16.70	26.5*	—	—	9.6*	22.4
<i>n</i> -Hexane	16.17	45.6	—	—	12.5*	17.8*
Chloroform	15.33	47.8	—	—	13.6*	18.2
CCl ₄	11.94	56.0	—	—	9.3	16.9

* are irregularities.

three readings. In Table II the values of heat of wetting are given when a known weight of naphthalene was added to the solvent. The heat of wetting slightly decreased in solvents: MeOH, EtOH, *n*-PrOH, *n*-BuOH, acetone and acetic acid, and increased in the other solvents studied when naphthalene was added to the solvent.

TABLE II

Solvent.	Heat of wetting in cal./g. when the following percentage of naphthalene was added by weight in 100 c.c. of the solvent.				
	1%	2%	3%	4%	5%
MeOH	33.80	33.76	33.70	33.73	33.58
EtOH	32.05	31.85	31.84	31.73	31.60
<i>n</i> -PrOH	31.01	30.98	30.76	30.58	—
<i>n</i> -BuOH	30.42	30.30	30.00	30.00	—
Acetone	30.02	30.01	30.04	30.08	—
Acetic acid	25.30	25.28	25.08	25.02	24.98
Benzene	18.6	18.8	18.52	18.62	19.30
Toluene	17.36	17.48	17.69	18.0	17.89
Chlorobenzene	16.9	16.96	16.56	16.40	—
<i>n</i> -Hexane	16.10	16.14	16.12	16.19	16.65
CHCl ₃	15.19	15.90	15.98	16.2	16.30
CCl ₄	12.6	12.82	12.53	12.9	13.00

DISCUSSION

From equation (3) it is seen that if the heat of wetting is large, adhesion tension of the liquid against the solid will also be large. It is observed from the values of the heat of wetting given in Table I that the heat of wetting of MeOH is large and so adhesion tension will also be large, and it will be large for all substances containing polar groups like —COOH, —CHO, —CN, —NH₂, —CONH₂ etc. according to Harkins (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42** 700), and will be less for hydrocarbons and other saturated compounds. Therefore, according to the argument given above, adhesion tension will be large for acids (benzoic, *o*-nitrobenzoic and phthalic acids) and less for hydrocarbons (naphthalene and acenaphthene).

Suppose a small amount of a solute, B, is added to the pure solvent. Adsorption occurs in a finite time. At zero time, that is before the adsorption, the concentration is greater than that after adsorption. There will also be the desorption of A, the solvent. The free energy change in this step No. (I) will be

$$\Delta F = \Delta F_a + \Delta F_b \quad \dots (I)$$

where ΔF is the free energy change due to change in concentration of the solution as a result of adsorption of B, and ΔF_a is that due to the desorption of A. ΔF_b is a negative quantity, as some quantity of B is removed from the solution by adsorption, and ΔF_a is a positive quantity.

But when B displaces A from the surface, there will be a change in free surface energy. The decrease of free energy due to the adsorption of B is ($a'A_{s-b}$) and the increase due to adsorption of A is ($a'A_{s-a}$), where a' is the area on the adsorbent which

was formerly occupied by A but is now taken up by B , and (A_{s-b}) and (A_{s-a}) are the adhesion tensions of B and A respectively. The total change is of course the sum of two changes (step II). This will be very small in the case when B is any acid (as in this case adhesion tensions will be nearly equal) and the solvent is also polar as stated above, and in the case of hydrocarbons this difference will be large when the solvent is polar.

As the concentration of B is further increased, the free energy decrease due to dilution of B through adsorption of it will become smaller and smaller, and a time will come when this will be equal to the increase of free energy due to displacement of A . The state of equilibrium between the adsorption of solute and solvent will be reached only when there is no total energy change in both steps No. (I) and (II) combined.

Now, when the change in step (II) is small, as in acids due to nearly equal adhesion tension, the state of equilibrium will be reached very soon and the equilibrium will be attained sooner, the larger is the heat of wetting or the energy change during desorption which will be numerically the same as during adsorption. Therefore, less adsorption of acids will occur from the solutions the solvent of which has a high heat of wetting. Berl and Wachendorff (*Kolloid Z., Zsigmondy Festschrift, 1925, 36*) also concluded the same thing. Gurvitch (*Kolloid Z., 1923, 32, 80*) also found an inverse qualitative relationship between heat of wetting of the solvent and the sorption of benzoic acid from it.

In the case of naphthalene and acenaphthene, energy change of step (II) is also remarkable and so nearly whole of the energy due to adsorption of A ($a'A_{s-a}$) is to be compensated by the energy of dilution of B , and as it becomes smaller and smaller as the concentration of B increases, it will be compensated only when large quantities of A are desorbed, and therefore here amounts of B adsorbed will be large. So, as the heat of wetting increases, adsorption of naphthalene and acenaphthene and other hydrocarbons also increases and *vice versa*.

From the data given in Table I, it is observed that as the heat of wetting decreases, the adsorption of naphthalene and acenaphthene also decreases, but in acids the case is reverse. Chlorobenzene, *n*-hexane and CHCl_3 behave differently in some cases.

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